

Phytochemical Investigation on the Root and Stem of *Naregamia Alata*, Wight.

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Naregamia alata, Wight. (Fam. Meliaceae; Sanskrit—Kandalu; Marathi—Pitpapra) is indigenous to India and is found in Konkan, N. Kanara, and Western Ghats of Madras State¹. The roots of *N. alata*, obtained from East Indies, is commercially known as Goanese ipecac². The root is a good emetic and cholagogue and has been found useful in acute dysentery and as an expectorant³. The plant is also used in rheumatism and itch⁴.

The root of *Naregamia alata*, Wight. is reported to contain naregamine, an amorphous alkaloid. The root-bark also contains wax, gum, asparagin, and starch⁵. The present investigation deals with the isolation and identification of crystalline constituents obtained from light petroleum extract of the root and stem of *N. alata*. Four crystalline substances have been isolated from the light petroleum extract and identified as heneicosane, β -sitosterol, stearic acid, and palmitic acid.

Procedure.—The powder (35 g.) of the root and stem together was successively extracted in a Soxhlet extractor with the usual solvents. The percentage yields of various extractives are: petroleum (b. p. 60-80°), 2.00; ether, 0.60; chloroform, 0.03; benzene, 0.03; ethanol (95%), 4.00; water, 3.00. The first four extracts exhibited a common yellowish green fluorescence.

Petroleum Extract.—The powdered root and stem of the dried plant were extracted with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°). Most of the solvent from the extract was removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the remainder by spontaneous evaporation. Solvent treatment of the resultant semisolid mass did not provide any definite product. A portion of the semisolid mass was therefore saponified with ethanolic potash and the nonsaponifiable matter was extracted with ether. Both the nonsaponifiable and saponifiable matters were then examined.

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1. Chopra, Nayar, and Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, p. 174.
2. Claus, "Pharmacognosy", Lea and Febiger, Philadelphia, 1959, p. 328.
3. Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. I, Lalit Mohan Basu, Allahabad, 1933, p. 536.
4. Watt, "Dictionary of the Economic Products of India", Vol. V, Superintendent of Govt. Printing Press, Calcutta, 1891, p. 342.
5. Nadkarri, "Indian Materia Medica", Vol. I, Popular Book Depot, Bombay, 1954, pp. 254, 256, 322.
7. Twitchell, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, **13**, 806.
7. Allen, "Commercial Organic Analysis", Vol. II, J. & A Churchill Ltd., London, 1948, p. 774.

Isolation of Heneicosane.—Treatment of the nonsaponifiable matter with ethanol separated a brownish solid which after successive treatment with ethyl acetate, ethanol, methanol, and light petroleum furnished a crystalline substance (A), m.p. 40.5-41°.

The substance (A) is a colorless crystalline compound, soluble in most of the organic solvents. It did not respond to tests for sterols, it did not react with acetic anhydride, hydroxylamine hydrochloride, alkaline potassium permanganate, or with bromine in chloroform. The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of heneicosane was undepressed. (Found: C, 85.04; H, 14.8; M.W. (Rast), 290. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{44}$: C, 85.1; H, 14.9%; M.W., 296].

Isolation of β Sitosterol.—After removal of the substance (A) from the ethanolic filtrate, the mother liquor was concentrated and evaporated spontaneously to a semisolid mass which was dissolved in acetone and kept in a refrigerator overnight, when a yellow crystalline substance separated. This substance on repeated crystallisations from methanol furnished colorless flakes of the substance (B), m.p. 136-37°.

Substance (B) is soluble in most of the organic solvents. It dissolved in H_2SO_4 (conc.), developing an orange-red colour with green fluorescence and responded to characteristic tests of sterols such as Burchard-Lieberman, Moleschotts, and Salkowski tests. The mixed m.p. with an authentic β -sitosterol remained underpressed. [Found: C, 84.05; H, 12.13; M.W. (Rast), 410. Calc. for $C_{29}H_{50}O$: C, 84.01; H, 12.15%; M.W., 414.7].

Acetylation and benzylation of the substance (B) afforded its acetate, m.p. 125° (Found: C, 81.51; H, 11.60. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.49; H, 11.48%) and benzoate, m.p. 146-47° (Found: C, 83.40; H, 10.62. Calc. for $C_{35}H_{54}O_2$: C, 81.35; H, 10.48%).

Isolation of Stearic and Palmitic Acids.—On acidifying with HCl, the aqueous solution of the saponifiable matter, fatty acids precipitated were extracted with water. The ethereal solution was washed with water, treated with anhydrous sodium sulphate, and evaporated to dryness.

The fatty acids were separated into solid and liquid fractions by Twitchell's lead acetate method⁷. Saturated acids, on fractional crystallisations from 95% ethanol, provided two substances. These on repeated crystallisations afforded a substance (C), m.p. 67.5-68.5° and a substance (D), m.p. 63-64°. Substance (C) is a colorless crystalline compound.

Substances (C) and (D) have been identified from analysis and mixed m.p. as stearic and palmitic acid respectively. Further work on other extracts is in progress.

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